

Performance Based Exploratory Data Analysis On Olympics Data Using Python

¹ Neeraj Yadav, ² Dr. J. Presis Jessintha

^{1,2} Pondicherry University Karaikal Campus, India

¹neeraj1372001@gmail.com, ²presisjessintha@gmail.com

Abstract:

Olympic Games is one of the most famous event in the world. More than 200 countries participate in this game to achieve medals for their countries. Each and every time the winners may vary and the number of medals thus secured varies according to their performance. Analysing the performance of the competitors is very much needed for the future competitions. The primary objective of this proposed work is to analyse the overall performance of the competitor using python libraries & machine learning algorithm. Analysis need to be done by each country to evaluate the previous performance and to find the challenges faced by the competitors that will help them to improve in future. Visualization of data set in many aspect provide the status of country in Olympic games and also help in inferring knowledge about the performance. This analysis is very much helpful in finding the area of improvement in the future. In this proposed method KNN & Random Forest machine learning algorithm is used and exploratory data analysis (EDA) owned on Olympic dataset is made to get appropriate result. With the above result, we can tell which country has the higher probability of getting more medals. Python-Numpy, Pandas, Matplotlib, Seaborn, API-Streamlit, KNN, Random Forest algorithm are the tools and techniques used in this proposed work.

Keywords: Data analysis, Data Visualization, Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA), Numpy, Pandas, Matplotlib, Seaborn, KNN & Random Forest Algorithm